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NERSC Technical Report no. 256
under Research Council of Norway contract no. 152710/730

SATELLITE EARTH OBSERVATION ATLAS FOR THE KARA SEA 1998 - 2004

ANNUAL REPORT 2004 UNDER THE PROJECT
MATERIAL FLUXES FROM THE RUSSIAN RIVERS OB' AND YENISEI:
INTERACTIONS WITH CLIMATE EFFECTS ON ARCTIC SEAS (MAREAS)

by

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Bergen, February 9, 2005

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REPORT

TITLE Satellite Earth Observation Atlas for the Kara Sea 1998 - 2004	REPORT No. Technical report no. 256
CLIENT Research Council of Norway / University of Oslo, Dept of Biology	CONTRACT No. 152710/730
CONTACT PERSONS Inger-Ann Ulstein / Dag Hessen	AVAILABILITY Open
AUTHORS Lasse H. Pettersson ¹⁾ , Dmitry Pozdnyakov ²⁾ and Anton Korosov ²⁾	DATE February 9, 2005
TASK PARTNERS 1) Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway 2) Nansen International Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, St. Petersburg Russia	
APPROVAL Lasse H. Pettersson	 Ola M. Johannessen, Director

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1 Introduction

A significant warming predicted in the Arctic in the 21st century is expected to appreciably affect the Arctic Ocean system and the ambient terrestrial and aquatic environments.

Characterized by limited biodiversity, and short food chains, the Arctic ecosystems are particularly vulnerable to environmental alterations. These are being driven presently and will be even more strongly accelerated in the future by fluctuations of numerous factors of both thermohydrodynamic and bio-geochemical nature.

The Arctic Ocean, first and foremost in its marginal environments are particularly susceptible to multifaceted alterations as they are accentuated by the freshwater input fluctuations due to climate change. Indeed, the Arctic Seas receive about 10% of the global river runoff (Aagaard and Carmack, 1993). Strong river runoff is conducive, in turn, to significant input of nutrients and organic matter. The latter undergoes versatile transformations both on the extensive continental shelves and in the course of freshwater masses off-shelf transport to pelagic areas of the interior Arctic basin.

In this respect, as a recipient of two largest rivers that flow into the Arctic, the Kara Sea is particularly affected by fresh water fluxes and associated inputs of nutrients and humic matter.

Significant efforts have been undertaken to investigate the riverine impacts on the Kara Sea and ultimately on the adjacent Arctic Ocean interior areas from board research vessels. Under the Siberian River Run-off (SIRRO) project a series of expeditions has been conducted between 1997 and 2002 (Levitan, and Schoster, 2004). Later, a cruise organized under another Norwegian-Russian joint project “Material fluxes from the Russian Rivers Ob and Yenisey: Interactions with climate and effects on Arctic Seas” (MAREAS) was performed in 2003 also on the same RV.

Regardless of the aforementioned cruising activities, the field data cover suffers from undersampling and low spatial-temporal resolution.

Satellite remote sensing in the visible region of the spectrum is known as an efficient means of collecting water quality data with sufficiently higher than shipborne data spatial and temporal resolution under cloudless conditions.

However, the Kara Sea proves to be infrequently screened by heavy cloudiness in the ice free-period (August-September). Notwithstanding this predicament, remote sensing data provides some supplementary information, which in combination with shipborne measurements increases the body of knowledge about the water quality in the Kara Sea and further out in the adjacent areas of the Arctic Ocean.

The present report is made under the MAREAS project and reflects our activities performed in 2004, primarily devoted to the development of a satellite Earth observation (EO) atlas of the marine distribution of chlorophyll *a*, suspended sediments and dissolved organic compounds in the Kara Sea during the ice free season of the years 1998 to 2004.

2 Characterization of satellite EO data sources

The data were downloaded from two satellite Earth Observation (EO) sensors, namely the so called ocean colour sensors SeaWiFS (Sea-viewing wide field of view sensor) and MODIS (Moderate Resolutions Imaging Spectrometer). The optical satellite data are collected in the respectively spectral channels with the central wavelengths (in nm) at: 412; 443; 490; 510; 555; 675; 765; 865 (SeaWiFS) and 412; 443; 488; 531; 551; 667; 678; 865 (MODIS).

The dates, on which high quality (i.e. cloud and haze free) SeaWiFS and MODIS images were available over the Kara Sea are listed in Table 1. As seen, the entire period of satellite monitoring extends from 1998 to 2004.

However, because of unfavourable weather conditions/heavy cloudiness screening, the overall number of useful images is only about 200 during the six years of available satellite data. Their temporal distribution is uneven also due to the aforementioned reasons. The major part of the satellite data falls into the time interval August-September, where the Kara Sea water is ice free.

Table 1. Dates of satellite overpasses of the Kara Sea, image names and attribution to satellite sensors (S stands for SeaWiFS, A stands for MODIS).

Date	Image Name	Date	Image Name
27.06.1998	S1998178095940	23.06.2001	S2001174102334
04.07.1998	S1998185101624	23.06.2001	S2001174120128
06.07.1998	S1998187100734	24.06.2001	S2001175110625
08.07.1998	S1998189095830	25.06.2001	S2001176101059
12.07.1998	S1998193111755	02.07.2001	S2001183083605
20.07.1998	S1998201104029	02.07.2001	S2001183101359
24.07.1998	S1998205102229	09.07.2001	S2001190083929
04.08.1998	S1998216102028	10.07.2001	S2001191110014
21.08.1998	S1998233095141	14.07.2001	S2001195103406
04.08.1999	S1999216094721	15.07.2001	S2001196111638
05.08.1999	S1999217085337	16.07.2001	S2001197102113
05.08.1999	S1999217103153	23.07.2001	S2001204102423
06.08.1999	S1999218093728	24.07.2001	S2001205110655
06.08.1999	S1999218111626	05.08.2001	S2001217094832
07.08.1999	S1999219084309	08.08.2001	S2001220101751
08.08.1999	S1999220092735	09.08.2001	S2001221110045
08.08.1999	S1999220110634	10.08.2001	S2001222100447
09.08.1999	S1999221101205	12.08.2001	S2001224095150
10.08.1999	S1999222091747	16.07.2002	S2002197100722
10.08.1999	S1999222105639	18.07.2002	A2002199063000
24.08.1999	S1999236080833	19.07.2002	A2002200053500
25.08.1999	S1999237085308	21.07.2002	A2002202070000
18.07.2000	S2000200104834	22.07.2002	A2002203060500

Date	Image Name	Date	Image Name
19.07.2000	S2000201095308	22.07.2002	S2002203105851
19.07.2000	S2000201113123	23.07.2002	S2002204100212
20.07.2000	S2000202103727	24.07.2002	S2002205104255
21.07.2000	S2000203111958	29.07.2002	S2002210105340
22.07.2000	S2000204102521	30.07.2002	S2002211095630
24.07.2000	S2000206101349	30.07.2002	S2002211113448
25.07.2000	S2000207105706	08.08.2002	S2002220111429
27.07.2000	S2000209104537	16.08.2002	S2002228101229
29.07.2000	S2000211103407	17.08.2002	S2002229105406
29.07.2000	S2000211121249	18.08.2002	S2002230095659
30.07.2000	S2000212111737	22.08.2002	A2002234070000
02.08.2000	S2000215101111	23.08.2002	S2002235100741
06.08.2000	S2000219094800	26.08.2002	A2002238063500
06.08.2000	S2000219112655	08.09.2002	A2002251060500
07.08.2000	S2000220103142	09.09.2002	A2002252051000
10.08.2000	S2000223110359	11.09.2002	A2002254063500
11.08.2000	S2000224100844	14.09.2002	A2002257070500
12.08.2000	S2000225105229	16.09.2002	A2002259051500
13.08.2000	S2000226095712	20.09.2002	A2002263063000
22.08.2000	S2000235095435	27.09.2002	A2002270063500
28.09.2002	A2002271054000	22.09.2003	A2003265054500
30.09.2002	A2002273070500	17.06.2004	A2004169051500
01.10.2002	A2002274061000	17.06.2004	A2004169065500
25.06.2003	A2003176055000	18.06.2004	A2004170060000
06.07.2003	A2003187071000	18.06.2004	S2004170104519
07.07.2003	A2003188061500	22.06.2004	A2004174053500
08.07.2003	A2003189052000	22.06.2004	A2004174221000
11.07.2003	A2003192055000	24.06.2004	A2004176003000
12.07.2003	A2003193063500	24.06.2004	A2004176070000
19.07.2003	S2003200111445	25.06.2004	A2004177060500
21.07.2003	S2003202105812	25.06.2004	S2004177103442
22.07.2003	A2003203071000	26.06.2004	A2004178051000
22.07.2003	S2003203100101	02.07.2004	A2004184061000
23.07.2003	A2003204061500	03.07.2004	A2004185051500
23.07.2003	S2003204104137	03.07.2004	A2004185065500
23.07.2003	S2003204121951	03.07.2004	S2004185110424
24.07.2003	A2003205052000	05.07.2004	S2004187104719
24.07.2003	S2003205112215	06.07.2004	A2004188005500
28.07.2003	A2003209045500	06.07.2004	S2004188112742
28.07.2003	A2003209063500	07.07.2004	A2004189000000

Date	Image Name	Date	Image Name
28.07.2003	S2003209122740	07.07.2004	A2004189063000
29.07.2003	A2003210054000	08.07.2004	A2004190221000
30.07.2003	S2003211121104	09.07.2004	S2004191101319
31.07.2003	A2003212070500	09.07.2004	S2004191115107
02.08.2003	S2003214105648	10.07.2004	A2004192003000
04.08.2003	A2003216064000	10.07.2004	A2004192070000
04.08.2003	S2003216104012	10.07.2004	A2004192233500
05.08.2003	A2003217054500	10.07.2004	S2004192105339
06.08.2003	S2003218102340	11.07.2004	A2004193060500
06.08.2003	S2003218120224	11.07.2004	A2004193224000
07.08.2003	A2003219071000	12.07.2004	A2004194051000
07.08.2003	S2003219110442	12.07.2004	S2004194103640
08.08.2003	A2003220061500	14.07.2004	A2004196063500
08.08.2003	S2003220100700	18.07.2004	A2004200061000
09.08.2003	A2003221052000	19.07.2004	A2004201051500
09.08.2003	S2003221104808	19.07.2004	A2004201065500
11.08.2003	A2003223064500	19.07.2004	S2004201102554
11.08.2003	S2003223103133	22.07.2004	S2004204105024
12.08.2003	A2003224055000	02.08.2004	S2004215114256
13.08.2003	S2003225101458	03.08.2004	S2004216104500
14.08.2003	S2003226105604	05.08.2004	A2004218060000
23.08.2003	A2003235071000	05.08.2004	S2004218102757
24.08.2003	A2003236061500	08.08.2004	A2004221063000
28.08.2003	A2003240055000	08.08.2004	S2004221105144
01.09.2003	A2003244070500	11.08.2004	A2004224070000
05.09.2003	A2003248064000	12.08.2004	A2004225060500
06.09.2003	A2003249054500	12.08.2004	S2004225101737
10.09.2003	A2003253052000	13.08.2004	A2004226051000
11.09.2003	A2003254060500	14.08.2004	A2004227010000
12.09.2003	A2003255051000	15.08.2004	A2004228063500
17.09.2003	A2003260070500	15.08.2004	S2004228104127
18.09.2003	A2003261061000	27.08.2004	A2004240070000
21.09.2003	A2003264064000	28.08.2004	A2004241060500
23.07.2004	A2004205063000	04.09.2004	A2004248061000
24.07.2004	S2004206103212	05.09.2004	A2004249065500
29.07.2004	S2004211103832	12.09.2004	A2004256070000
30.07.2004	A2004212063500	13.09.2004	A2004257060500
02.08.2004	A2004215070500		

3 Description of the image processing algorithm

This is a new operational algorithm for the retrieval of water quality from optical remote sensing data for both clear and turbid waters (Pozdnyakov et al, in press 2005). It contains an array of neural networks providing input for the Levenberg-Marquardt multivariate optimization procedure as the final retrieval tool. With a given accuracy threshold, the developed algorithm is sufficiently robust to data with noise up to 15 per cent for certain hydro-optical conditions. To avoid inadequate retrieval results, the algorithm identifies and eventually discards the pixels with inadequate atmospheric correction and/or water optical properties incompatible with the applied hydro-optical model. This procedure also identifies coccolith expressions. Examples of practical applications of the developed algorithm are given.

Only *visible* radiation appreciably penetrates into the water column (e.g. Jerlov, 1976). Travelling through the aquatic medium, photons are subject of a variety of interactions with the encountered molecules, which often leads to essential alterations of the spectral composition of the upwelling radiative flux (e.g. Pozdnyakov and Grassl, 2003). Thus, the backscattered flux emerging from beneath the water surface contains the information about the optical properties of the water column. The water colour is a convolution of all interactions of photons with the aquatic medium. Therefore, satellite optical sensors are in principle able to observe in-water parameters and associated processes (Kondratyev *et al.*, 1999).

In the case of open ocean waters, the algorithms for the retrieval of the desired water quality parameter(s) are rather unsophisticated semi-analytical ones (e.g. the OC4 algorithm currently used by NASA (O'Reilly *et al.*, 1998; Ackleson, 2001)). This is possible due to the optical simplicity of such waters, referred to as case I waters by Morel and Prieur (1977). Open ocean water is generally only loaded with indigenous phytoplankton and their *retinue*, i.e. accompanying and co-varying products of their life cycles as well as some microscopic organisms such as flagellates, bacteria and viruses, which are also indigenous to off-shore/mid-oceanic waters (Sathyendranath, 2000). Therefore, spectral variations in upwelling radiance must to be strictly proportional to the concentration of phytoplankton, or its proxy - the concentration of chlorophyll (*chl*) contained in algal cells. In this case a relationship can be established between the concentration of chlorophyll and the emerging radiance at two or more wavelengths normalized by the incident irradiance at the same wavelengths.

However, waters in the coastal zone as well as inland waters, referred to as case II waters by Morel and Prieur (1977) are characterized by optical properties that are influenced not only by the indigenous phytoplankton (chlorophyll *a*) and the substances originating from the phytoplankton's life cycle, but also by other matters independent of phytoplankton (denoted herein as *chl*), notably inorganic/terrigenous particulate matter in suspension (*sm*) and dissolved organics (*doc*). Their content in the water column is often abundant enough to compete with phytoplankton in influencing the resultant optical properties of Case II waters, thus rendering such waters optically very complex. Accordingly it is a challenge to discriminate between the contributions to these optical active compounds to the total spectral signal measured by the satellite sensor.

When observing case II waters from above, it is impossible to retrieve the concentration of a single component (e.g. *chl*) without also inferring simultaneously the content of the other major water constituents influencing water colour, the so called colour producing agents (CPAs) encompassing first and foremost *chl*, *sm* and *doc* (Bukata *et al.*, 1995). These constituents are traditionally associated with *water quality parameters* (WQP), although more

substances contribute to these (Anonymous, 1992). Thus, case II waters complicate significantly the retrieval of the CPAs by remote sensing.

Another complicating factor is the inaccurate atmospheric correction (Land and Haigh, 1997; Ruddick *et al.*, 2000). The major challenge here is an accurate assessment of the path radiance originating from photon interactions with the atmospheric aerosol, especially with the aerosol in the lower troposphere.

The atmospheric aerosol over case I waters is generally homogeneous spatially and chemically both in the upper and lower troposphere. It is mostly marine particulate matter, and its influence on light transfer is largely by scattering. Its optical properties are established fairly well and, hence, can be adequately assessed in the atmospheric correction procedure. The inaccuracy of water constituent retrievals arising from atmospheric correction errors over case I waters is about 5% (for refs. see Pozdnyakov *et al.*, 2000a).

In the atmosphere over case II waters the aerosol composition originates from a wealth of distributed and point sources, often anthropogenic. This results in a pronounced spatial and compositional inhomogeneity of the aerosol. In addition, the aerosol over such areas is no longer purely scattering but also absorbing. This complicates significantly the atmospheric correction (for refs. see Pozdnyakov *et al.*, 2000b).

In general, the error in atmospheric correction can be distributed either uniformly or normally and its level can depend on and be independent of wavelength λ . The scarce reports indicate that the error in upwelling radiance arising from imperfect atmospheric correction over case II waters can be as high as 15 % in the short wavelength region diminishing nearly linearly with λ .

Earlier we reported (Pozdnyakov and Lyaskovsky, 1999) that under conditions of low noise input and availability of an adequate hydro-optical model the Levenberg-Marquardt (L-M) multivariate optimization procedure can successfully be used for the retrieval of CPAs in case II waters. However, the procedure performance is rather slow, which prevents using it for operational processing of satellite images. Neural networks (NN) used as a water constituent retrieval tool prove to be much faster, although they are inferior to the L-M procedure in terms of the attainable accuracy.

In the light of the above, a combination of the L-M and NN procedures might therefore lead to a fast-operating bio-optical algorithm, which would provide a high accuracy of CPA retrievals under conditions of comparably large measurement errors. We used the Stuttgart University software for creating our NN algorithm (SNNS, 1995).

As seen from Table 2 due to an essential narrowing of the range of initial concentrations C_0 (attained in the first step by the NN emulator), the L-M algorithm in the second step solves the inverse problem far more rapidly.

Table 2. A comparison of performance efficiency (in s/pixel) for the L-M procedure and the coupled NN→L-M sequence at a λ -independent 15% measurement error.

Procedure	L-M		NN→L-M		LM/(NN→L-M)	
	uniform	normal	uniform	normal	uniform	normal
$C_{sm} < 5 \text{ mg/l}$	0.030	0.011	0.003	0.002	9.3	5.0
$C_{sm} \subset (5 - 20) \text{ mg/l}$	0.121	0.042	0.003	0.002	43.6	21

The speed of the L-M procedure without a preceding NN narrowing the C_0 range significantly depends upon the concrete hydro-optical situation: as the concentration of sm decreases, the time required for the solution of the inverse problem (i.e. for the retrieval of the CPA concentration vector) also shortens. Understandably, the actual shortening entirely depends upon the power of the computer used. Contrarily, in the case of the above sequence of coupled (NN→L-M) procedures the dependence of the computation time on C_{sm} reduces to naught: it takes only several thousandths of a second to retrieve one CPA concentration vector (or otherwise, to process one pixel in a satellite image).

The principal scheme/flow-diagram of an advanced operational algorithm based upon the coupling between NN and L-M procedures is given in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. A flow-through diagram of the advanced bio-optical algorithm.

Having been subjected to a preliminary processing, also incorporating the atmospheric correction, the satellite image is further treated by calculating for each pixel calculated the corresponding subsurface remote sensing reflectance spectrum $R_{rsw}(\lambda)$ (Pozdnyakov *et al.*, 2003). First, the normalized upwelling radiance ($L_w(\lambda)$) is achieved on the basis of ancillary data, namely instantaneous extraterrestrial solar flux ($F_0(\lambda)$) and sun zenith angle θ_0 .

For each pixel, $R_{rsw}(\lambda)$ serves as input for the NN procedure (NN-1). If one of the CPA concentrations as determined by the NN-1 emulator falls in the concentration range 0-5 (in

respective units), a corresponding narrow-band neural network (NN-2, NN-3 or NN-4, see Fig.2) is started.

In the next step, the CPA concentration vector C_θ thus determined is used to get an array of initial concentrations C_0 . We have used the range from 0.7 to 1.3°C remembering that the maximal measurement error was set to 15 %.

From the created pool of initial concentrations C_0 , starting concentrations C_i for each CPA are randomly taken as input for the L-M procedure crowning the retrieval process.

If available for the water body under investigation, minimum and maximum concentrations of *chl*, *sm* and *doc* are imposed on the pursued multivariate search of the optimal CPA concentration vector (this option is not explicitly shown in Fig.1)

At the exit of the coupled NN→L-M sequence the final concentration values of *chl*, *sm* and *doc* emerge. The above retrieval algorithm functions only if a hydro-optical model appropriate for the water body amenable to remote sensing as well as a parametric relationship (e.g. Jerome *et al.*, 1996) relating $R_{rsw}(\lambda)$ and the water bulk absorption and backscattering coefficients a and b_b are available.

3.1 Quality assurance.

Our multistage algorithm has two quality assessment units. The first eliminates the pixels suffering from imprecise atmospheric correction. It manifests itself in *a*) negative values of R_{rsw} at short wavelengths (400-450 nm) due to an *overestimation* of the path radiance, and *b*) enhanced values of R_{rsw} in the blue part of the spectrum (channels 1 and 2 in the case of SeaWiFS) followed by a *dip* in either the second or third channel(s) due to an *underestimation* of the path radiance.

In comparison with case I waters, case II waters are generally loaded with appreciable amounts of *sm*. As a result, the R_{rsw} spectrum peaks at about 560 nm (channel 5 of SeaWiFS), on both sides of which it gradually decreases.

Therefore, we discard pixels with negative R_{rsw} values in the blue. Next we calculate the gradient of the processed R_{rsw} spectrum starting from the first channel (i.e. the shortest wavelength) and moving to the red portion of the spectrum. The pixel is preserved only if the corresponding spectrum exhibits a stable positive gradient at $\lambda < \sim 560$ nm (it is allowed to be just non-negative at $\lambda \leq 450$ nm), followed by a negative gradient for $\lambda > \sim 560$ nm. The pixel is discarded, if along with the long-wave maximum in the R_{rsw} spectrum there is a dip at shorter wavelengths. However, this mask does not discard, pixels with the R_{rsw} spectra characteristic of clear case I waters, should they be present in the image. Identification of case I and case II waters is performed through jointly analyzing both the envelope of R_{rsw} spectra and their mean spectral value. The latter is known (e.g. Bukata *et al.*, 1985) to be distinctly different for clear and turbid waters, and a corresponding threshold is used to this end.

The second quality assurance (mask) is intended to detect pixels corresponding to such areas of the water body under surveillance, whose hydro-optical properties significantly differ from those covered by the applied hydro-optical model. It might be due to either the area-specific composition of *doc*, and/or *sm* or the presence of some particular phytoplankton

species or their residuals (e.g. “red-tide” algae, coccoliths, *etc.*), which go beyond the scope of the employed hydro-optical model.

This second mask/flag operates as follows: as soon as the definitive concentration vector \mathbf{C} is established for the processed pixel, it is further used for the reconstruction of the corresponding R_{rsw} spectrum using the adopted both hydro-optical model and parametric relationship $R_{rsw} = f(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}_b)$. The reconstructed R_{rsw} spectrum (R_{rsw2} in Fig. 1) is then compared with the initial $R_{rsw}(\lambda)$ spectrum retrieved from the satellite data (R_{rsw1} in Fig. 1). If the mean spectral value of R_{rsw1} is significantly higher than R_{rsw2} , then the pixel can either be discarded or attributed to a coccoliths expressions. Coccoliths are known (e.g. Balch *et al.*, 1996) to appear *on or just below* the water surface as whitish and hence relatively bright spots surrounded on all sides by dark water. Therefore, the coccolith option comes into action provided the retrieved R_{rsw1} spectrum, in addition to its high values for the visible wavelengths, exhibits only a *weak* spectral variance [$\sim \lambda^{-\xi}$, $1 < \xi < 1.35$: see e.g. Balch *et al.*, 1996; Smyth *et al.* 2002]. The appropriate limits for departures of $R_{rsw1}(\lambda)$ from its mean spectral value are duly imposed.

Application of both quality assurance stages helps to eliminate from the retrieved spatial distributions of CPA the pixels/areas with erroneous concentrations of either *chl-a* or *sm* and *doc*. This inevitably results in the appearance of lacunas in the retrieved distributions. However, application of the well-known SURFER code (SURFER Brochure, 2004) facilitates the visual interpretation of such images by presenting them as a sequence of grey-scaled areas, the borders of which correspond to concentration isolines of the relevant CPA (see below).

When running the L-M procedure, the use of a normalized or absolute difference between S_i and R_{rsw1} to *simulated data* yields very similar retrieval results. However, this is not the case when the L-M procedure is applied to *life data* from satellite sounding. Indeed, unlike smooth simulated R_{rsw} data, life spectra of R_{rsw1} frequently are characterized by dips and/or steep increases/decreases, the nature of these features being variable and often reside in inaccurate atmospheric correction, but not only. The choice between normalized and absolute difference options becomes consequential, when the R_{rsw1} spectrum exhibits very low/nearly zero values in the blue part of the spectrum (e.g. the first one-two SeaWiFS channels), and rather high values in the middle of the visible spectral range. The problem resides in the applied hydro-optical models: at any CPA concentration vector \mathbf{C} , very low values of water volume reflectance (or remote sensing reflectance) at short wavelengths, λ are not followed by high values of this quantity at longer λ .

When the *relative* difference is applied, the L-M procedure tends to create a R_{rswII} spectrum, which fits most closely the R_{rsw1} spectrum in the first channels, through minimizing the greatest residuals. Understandably these are in the blue, given very low values of R_{rsw1} spectrum in the first channels. As a result, the L-M procedure ends up in yielding abnormally high values of C_{dom} as the only CPA encompassed by the hydro-optical model, which capable to crucially reduce the water column reflectance at short wavelengths. Understandably, the retrieved concentrations of *chl-a* and *sm* prove in this case to be also conspicuously incorrect.

When the absolute difference is applied, the L-M procedure, as a least-square method, tends to equally minimize the residuals at all λ /in all channels, and it ends up with creating a

$R_{rsw II}$ spectrum, which, in comparison with $R_{rsw I}$, is relatively enhanced in the blue, and subdued in the middle of the visible. Conceivably, this is also conducive to the retrieval of unrealistic CPA concentrations. We found that the problem can be successfully resolved if the relative difference is applied to the discussed type of $R_{rsw I}$ spectrum, provided the first one or two channels are discarded.

This option is also accommodated in the described algorithm through introducing a respective threshold for $R_{rsw I}$ values in the short wavelength region of the spectrum.

3.2 Concluding remarks

Thus our new more advanced algorithm for the retrieval of natural water quality can generally be utilized for both clear and turbid waters, but it is intended to be used preferably for processing satellite images over case II waters, which present a more serious challenge due to their enhanced optical complexity. For a successful performance of the developed algorithm an accurate atmospheric correction and an adequate hydro-optical model of the waters amenable to remote sensing are required.

Both requirements are often hard to be met. The major problem with atmospheric correction resides in the atmospheric aerosol, whose composition, optical properties and distribution are highly variable in space and time, especially over land areas and coastal zones.

The availability of adequate hydro-optical models for the remotely sensed water bodies is hampered by many reasons. Phytoplankton communities are complex and their composition is highly variable throughout vegetation seasons. They are very sensitive to the availability of nutrients, light climate and water temperature – the factors, which are subject to large spatial/temporal variations themselves.

Due to erosion of the soils in the watershed, suspended minerals are also area specific (Pozdnyakov and Grassl, 2003). In addition, weather conditions (dry or rainy periods) control not only the amounts of *sm* brought in, but also their microphysical properties (e.g., size distribution). The same applies to *doc*: the ratio between allochthonic and autochthonic *doc* is significantly dependent upon weather conditions.

On top, the existing hydro-optical models take account of only three major CPAs: *chl*, *sm* and *doc*, thus ignoring other matters such as bacterioplankton, zooplankton, detritus, and air bubbles. It was also shown (Pozdnyakov and Grassl, 2003) that some transspectral processes (fluorescence of *doc* and *chl-a* in the first place) could be important in forming bulk optical properties of the waters under study. This implies that the existing hydro-optical models should be extended to include such parameters as the fluorescence yield of *chl-a* and *doc*.

Finally, air bubbles originating from wind action but also produced by phytoplankton and, possibly, bacterioplankton present an unaccounted factor capable of contributing to the bulk backscattering of a water column. Although there are several reports on the optical properties of air bubbles (for ref. see e.g. Pozdnyakov and Grassl, 2003), to our knowledge, no appropriate models have been suggested so far to include air bubbles into the general scheme of photon interactions with the aquatic medium. In addition, bursting of air bubbles just above the water surface (Rossodivita, Andreussi, 1999) can constitute an unaccounted contribution to the light scattering in the atmosphere, which might be consequential for a precise assessment of the path radiance, and hence accurate atmospheric correction.

Naturally, the neglect of the above factors has to result in retrieval errors, the importance of which is not necessarily high, but still needs to be considered in concrete circumstances.

Ideally, individual hydro-optical models are required for each water body under satellite surveillance, and, so much so, for every vegetation season. This can, probably, be reached for large water bodies, but certainly not for small ones. In reality, the developed hydro-optical models are tentatively applied to neighboring water bodies assuming that they might be akin in terms of their optical properties, which is not necessarily the case.

The quality assurance units complementing the developed algorithm are intended to allay to a certain degree the problems arising from both imperfect atmospheric correction and inadequacy of hydro-optical models. However, their sole function consists in *eliminating* the wrong information rather than *overcoming* the essence of the problem.

Notwithstanding the above impediments, it could be advocated that the new algorithm can become a reliable basis for further improvement of remote sensing of optically complex natural waters.

4 Analysis of the Kara Sea ocean colour images during the 2003 MAREAS field expedition

The Kara Sea (for geographic location see Fig. 1) has a unique hydrological feature: it annually receives a record amount of fluvial waters ($\sim 1350 \text{ km}^3$), which is equivalent to a 1.52 m fresh water layer if spread throughout the entire area of the sea (Ivanov, 1997, Volkov *et al.* 2002). This accounts for about 56% of the total river runoff into the coastal seas of the Arctic Ocean. Such an extraordinary rate of fresh water supply into the Kara Sea is due to two inflowing great Siberian rivers, Ob and Yenisey: together with two other, much smaller rivers, Pyasina and Nizhnyaya Taymyra, they constitute 94,2% of the entire amount of fresh water entering into the Kara Sea.

Along with the river runoff impact, the hydrological regime in the Kara Sea is also affected by inflow of the Barents Sea (warm and nutrient-enrich) and Atlantic Ocean waters. However, the presence of the Novaya Zemlya and Vaygach Islands (Fig. 1) in the west, the Franz Josef Land in the north and Severnaya Zemlya in the east render the Kara Sea a relatively isolated water body, and thus accentuate the impact of river runoff on the hydrological regime as well as the trophic status of the sea (Matishov and Pavlova, 1990).

River waters in the Kara Sea expand over significant distances from the respective river mouths. Although there is a general transport of Arctic waters from the west to the east, the pattern of spread of freshened waters in the Kara Sea depends predominantly upon the prevailing winds, and thus can vary from year to year. Either fan-like (Fig.1a), or northern (Fig.1b) or else eastern (Fig.1c) options of distribution of desalinated waters in the Kara Sea can establish in summer (Fig. 1). At depth, under the freshened waters, there is a layer of salinity jump that restrains wind mixing and, hence, prevents the vertical dissipation of surface waters.

Figure 2. Types of patterns of spread of river runoff waters throughout the Kara Sea in summer: a- fan-like, b- northern, c- eastern; The numbers in the legend stand for: I-70-50%; II- 80-90%; 3- 80-90%; IV- >90% of desalination of marine waters;

Arabic figures (1-4) denote: 1- Novaya Zemlya Island, 2- Vaigatch Island, 3- Karskie Vorota Strait; 4- Yamal Peninsular; 5- Ob River, 6- Yenisey River, 7- vicinity of the Franz Josef Land, 8- Severnaya Zemlya Islands.

In summer, the surface waters contain between 50 and 70% of river water at the northern and north-western boundaries of the Kara Sea, whereas in the south this share can be in excess of 90%.

A persistent cyclonic circulation in the south-western part of the Kara Sea (between the Novaya Zemlya Island and the Yamal Peninsular) can draw the freshened waters off the northern part of the Novaya Zemlya down to the Karskie Vorota Strait and there also entraining the Barents Sea waters bring them further up to the Yamal Peninsular.

The swampy soils abundant within the watershed of the main rivers flowing into the Kara Sea result in bringing significant amounts of dissolved fractions of soil humus along with the river runoff. In addition, owing to land runoff and dynamic erosion of river banks and river beds, enhanced amounts of suspended matter and nutrients reach the Kara Sea and eventually become spread over its vast areas.

The above processes are expected to result in establishment of some specific hydrochemical and hydrobiological conditions in the Kara Sea. However, their investigation is seriously hampered by severe weather conditions and can only be performed during 2-3 months when in the Kara Sea there are sufficiently vast ice-free areas suitable for research vessel cruising.

Invariably suffering from undersampling, shipborne studies fail to produce the desired data at the spatial and temporal resolution required for attaining an adequate insight into the highly dynamic in-water processes in the sea.

Devoid of the above shortcomings, optical remote sensing from satellites, under favourable weather conditions, can efficiently contribute to the traditional shipborne means of studies for exploring the spatial and temporal variations in the water quality and trophic status of the Kara Sea.

Under the MAREAS Project, funded by the Norwegian Research Council, we collected, processed and thematically analyzed fourteen MODIS images taken over the Kara Sea between 05.08.2003 and 12.08.2003. The applied methodology, obtained results and ensuing discussion are presented below.

Utilization of satellite optical sensors for studying the Kara Sea is challenged by at least two major impediments. The first one arises from the fact discussed above that the Kara Sea waters are spatially highly heterogeneous being significantly influenced by massive inputs of terrigenous suspended and dissolved matters. Therefore, the coastal waters are definitely non-case I waters (according to the Morel classification (Morel and Prieur, 1977)) It implies that the standard MODIS algorithm designed for the retrieval of phytoplankton chlorophyll concentrations mostly in open ocean waters can hardly be suitable for the Kara Sea hydro-optical conditions. Besides, not only phytoplankton chlorophyll but also dissolved organic and water turbidity are important parameters for a better understanding of the trophic status dynamics in the sea. Therefore, some more sophisticated water quality retrieval techniques are likely to be eligible for this purpose.

For processing the MODIS images we applied our advanced operational algorithm based upon combining the neural network (NN) and the Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) multivariate procedures (see above). Having been subjected to a preliminary processing, also incorporating the atmospheric correction, the satellite image is further treated by calculating for each pixel calculated the corresponding subsurface remote sensing reflectance spectrum $R_{rsw}(\lambda)$

(Pozdnyakov *et al.* 2003). First, the normalized upwelling radiance ($L_w(\lambda)$) is achieved on the basis of ancillary data, namely instantaneous extraterrestrial solar flux ($F_0(\lambda)$) and sun zenith angle θ_0 , and is available from the MODIS level-2 data.

In conformity with the above description, for each pixel, $R_{rsw}(\lambda)$ serves as input for a broad-band NN procedure (NN-1): the concentrations of phytoplankton chlorophyll (*chl*), suspended minerals (*sm*) and dissolved organic matter (*doc*), assumed as the major colour-producing agents (CPAs) in natural water, were sought within the ranges (0-70 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$; 0-30 mg l^{-1} and 0-30 mg Cl^{-1} , respectively). If one of the CPA concentrations as determined by the NN-1 emulator falls in the concentration range 0-5 (in respective units), a corresponding narrow-band NN (NN-2, NN-3 or NN-4) is started.

In the next step, the CPA concentration vector C_0 thus determined is used to obtain an array of initial concentrations C_0 . We have used the range from 0.7 to 1.3 C assuming that the maximal measurement error is 15 % (Pozdnyakov *et al.*, 2004).

From the created pool of initial concentrations C_0 , starting concentrations C_i for each CPA are randomly taken as input for the LM procedure crowning the retrieval process.

If available for the water body under investigation, minimum and maximum concentrations of *chl*, *sm* and *doc* are imposed on the pursued multivariate search of the optimal CPA concentration vector.

At the exit of the coupled NN→LM sequence the final concentration values of *chl*, *sm* and *doc* emerge. The above retrieval algorithm functions only if a hydro-optical model appropriate for the water body amenable to remote sensing as well as a parametric relationship (e.g. Jerome *et al.* 1996) relating $R_{rsw}(\lambda)$ and the water bulk absorption and backscattering coefficients a and b_b are available. We used the hydro-optical model suggested by one of us for mesotrophic waters (Pozdnyakov and Grassl, 2003).

The other impediment challenging the accurate retrieval of CPAs is the atmospheric correction. The aerosol composition in the atmosphere over the Kara Sea (especially in summer time) can differ from the aerosol types encompassed by the lookup tables used by the MODIS atmospheric correction code. Besides, in summer, fogs not infrequently occur over the open water areas in the Kara Sea, and can, therefore, contaminate the path radiance, and eventually the legitimate signal captured by the satellite sensor.

Our multistage algorithm is outfitted with two quality assessment units. The first eliminates the pixels suffering from imprecise atmospheric correction. It manifests itself in *a*) negative values of R_{rsw} at short wavelengths (400-450 nm) due to an overestimation of the path radiance, and *b*) enhanced values of R_{rsw} in the blue part of the spectrum followed by a dip in either the second or third channel(s) due to an underestimation of the path radiance.

The second quality assurance is intended to dismiss/mask pixels corresponding to such areas of the water body under surveillance, whose hydro-optical properties significantly differ from those covered by the applied hydro-optical model. It might be due to either the area-specific composition of *doc*, and/or *sm* or the presence of some particular phytoplankton species or their residuals, which go beyond the scope of the employed hydro-optical model.

Due to the interference of cloudiness over the Kara Sea in August, 2003, only fourteen MODIS images (taken between August 5-12) proved to be useful, but none of them was completely free of cloud-screened areas. To obtain spatial distributions of the CPAs (i.e. *chl*, *sm* and *doc*) throughout the entire sea, the results of CPA retrievals were merged and respective composites were generated. To calculate the mean value of each of the CPAs in a pixel, used were the respective CPA concentrations in this pixel retrieved from all images with this pixel “free” of cloudiness.

4.1 Results of retrieval and discussion

The results of retrieval of the spatial and temporal averaged *chl*, *sm* and *doc* distribution in the Kara Sea as obtained through the application of our above approach are illustrated in Figs. 3-5.

Fig. 3. The spatial and temporal averaged distribution of chl-a as retrieved from the MODIS images over the Kara Sea, during the period 5-12 August 2003.

The adequacy of the retrievals attained through applying our advanced algorithm can be assessed from a comparison of the reported shipborne *in situ* determinations of CPA concentrations (Nöthing *et al.* 2003; Köhler *et al.* 2003; Gaye-Haake *et al.*, 2003). As seen from Fig. 3, the *chl-a* concentration distribution in the Kara Sea implies that in the summer of 2003 is indicative that the predominant winds determined a distinctively eastern spread of river runoff waters, predominantly from the Ob and Yenisey Rivers. The concurrent spatial distributions of *sm* and *doc* comply perfectly with this corollary: both constituents are most abundant to the east from the Ob River estuary and adhere to the coastal zone between the Yamal Peninsular and the Severnaya Zemlya Islands (compare with Fig. 2c).

Accordingly, the northern area of the south-western region of the Kara Sea is fairly devoid of river waters, poorly productive, and the river-driven *doc* and *sm* concentrations are very low there.

Fig. 4. The spatial and temporal averaged distribution of sm as retrieved from the MODIS images over the Kara Sea, during the period 5-12 August 2003.

At the same time, as seen in the south west (low left-hand) part of Figs. 3 and 5, the warm Barents Sea waters appear as rich in *chl-a* and contain appreciable amounts of *doc*, thus confirming their a rather high trophic status. Figs. 3-5 are also indicative that in the south-western region of the Kara Sea there are areas extending from the Karskie Vorota Strait to the northern coast of the Yamal Peninsular. As has been pointed out above, there is a persistent cyclonic circulation in the south-western part of the Kara Sea can entrain the productive Barents Sea waters off the northern part of the Novaya Zemlya down to the Karskie Vorota Strait and then further up to the Yamal Peninsular.

Fig. 5. The spatial and temporal averaged distribution of doc as retrieved from the MODIS images over the Kara Sea, during the period 5-12 August 2003.

The *chl-a* concentrations as retrieved from the MODIS data (Fig. 3) vary in rather wide ranges, reaching in some locations 23 $\mu\text{g/l}$. According to Nöthing *et al.* (2003) in some years (e.g. 1999) *in situ* measurements gave *chl-a* maximum concentrations up to 13-15 $\mu\text{g/l}$.

The retrieved *doc* concentrations also are very variable with the maximum values up to 20 mgC/l. The available *in situ* data (Kohler *et al.*, 2003) indicate that the maximum *doc* levels were registered at ~13-15 mgC /l.

According to our spaceborne data, in some areas the maximum *sm* concentrations are 3-4 mg/l. Gaye *et al.* (2003) report that the total suspended matter in the waters of the region under discussion can be up to *ca* 4.7 mg/l with the inorganic component accounting for up to *ca* 72%.

Thus, the above comparisons of *in situ* and retrieved data indicate that the spatial patterns in *chl-a*, *sm* and *doc* distributions comply very closely with the known oceanographic data. Discrepancies in the absolute values of *in situ* measured and retrieved concentrations of CPAs are believed owing to the fact that the hydro-optical model used in our algorithm has not been developed specifically for the Kara Sea. This inevitably is bound to introduce some systematic retrieval errors, leaving, however, the general features of the CPA spatial distribution patterns quite adequate.

Consequently, the simultaneously recovered spatial distributions of *chl-a*, *sm* and *doc* (Figs. 3-5) are believed to be the first trustworthy images of water quality parameter fields in the Kara Sea obtained from space reflecting the impact of river runoff impact on the trophy of the sea.

5 Publications resulting from the research conducted under the MAREAS project

Pozdnyakov, D. V., A.A. Korosov, L.H. Pettersson and O.M. Johannessen, 2005, MODIS evidences the river runoff impact on the Kara Sea Trophy. *International Journal of Remote Sensing* (in print - 2005).

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7 ANNEXES: The Kara Sea images (both SeaWiFS and MODIS) processed and analysed for the period 1998-2004

7.1 Merely processed individual images of chlorophyll-a (chl-a), suspended minerals (sm) and dissolved organic compound (doc) components (see Annex I in the file "annex1.pdf" – 201 pages)

7.2 Monthly averaged images of chlorophyll-a (chl-a), suspended minerals (sm) and dissolved organic compound (doc) components (see Annex II in the file "annex2.pdf" – 20 pages)

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